

C⁰-TYPE EFFICIENT HIGHER-ORDER PLATE THEORY FOR THE THERMO-MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

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1 Introduction

Recently, various engineering applications demand lightweight and high stiffness structures. So, advanced laminated composite plates have been rapidly and widely used in automobile and aerospace engineering as well as in other engineering fields because of their high stiffness to weigh ratio and it's durability.

To accurately predict their static and dynamic response, numerous composite plate theories developed in last three decades, such as well-known conventional theories(CLPT; classical laminated plate theory, FSDT; first order shear deformation theory) and many other refined higher order shear deformation theories [1]. However, most of them have a defect which can't satisfy transverse shear stress conditions.

On the other hands, various zig-zag plate theories have also been developed to improve their accuracy and compatibility. Among others, the efficient higher-order plate theory(EHOPT) [2], which satisfy the transverse shear conditions(stress free at top and bottom surface and stress continuity at interfaces) by superimposing linear zig-zag field to the globally cubic in-plane displacement field, has been considered as the best 5 D.O.F model. However, derivatives of out-of-plane displacement field were contained in the in-plane displacement fields of the EHOPT, so that it requires to C¹ continuity in their finite element implementation, which result in computational effort.

In order to improve the numerical issue, C⁰-type zig-zag theory was proposed by Wanji et al [3]. They give simple method to construct C⁰ continuous finite element based on C⁰-type zig-zag theory by

employing shear free conditions at the top and bottom surface to eliminate derivatives of out-of-plane displacement field from the in-plane displacement fields.

Although C⁰-type zig-zag theory gives reliable results for the mechanical loading problems, it was developed under the plane stress assumption in which transverse normal strain effect is neglected. However, transverse normal strain effect plays a significant role in thermal loading problems. This brings us to develop a new C⁰-type efficient higher-order plate theory via the mixed formulation, including transverse normal strain effect, for the analysis of laminated composite plates under thermo-mechanical loads. By assuming out-of-plane displacement field as parabolic distribution, proposed theory will allow us to analyze accurately the thermo-mechanical behavior of the laminated composite plates.

In this paper, as a new way to address the aforementioned issues, the C⁰-type efficient higher-order plate theory via the mixed formulation is developed and tested numerically. The main objective herein is to systematically set-up the relationship between the C⁰-type efficient higher-order plate theory and the seventh-order zig-zag model, and to eliminate derivatives of out-of-plane displacement field from the in-plane displacements fields of the EHOPT by employing transverse shear stress conditions. And out-of-plane displacement field is assumed to be a smooth parabolic distribution through the thickness direction to consider transverse normal strain effect. Finally the results obtained herein are compared with those of other theories reported in literature.

2 C⁰-type EHOPT formulation

In this paper we consider laminated composite plates of thickness h , which are made of monoclinic materials. Geometry and coordinates of the laminated composite plate is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Geometry and coordinates of laminated plate

The shear strain relationship is established by employing the mixed variational theorem(MVT) [4]. Independent displacement and stress fields are assumed in MVT. The displacement fields are taken from the C⁰-type efficient higher-order plate theory, while the stress fields are obtained from the seventh-order zig-zag model.

The initial displacement fields of third-order zig-zag theory can be written as follows,

$$u_{\alpha} = u_{\alpha}^o + \psi_{\alpha} x_3 + \xi_{\alpha} x_3^2 + \phi_{\alpha} x_3^3 + \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} S_{\alpha}^{(k)} (x_3 - x_{3(k)}) H(x_3 - x_{3(k)}), \quad (1)$$

$$u_3 = u_3^o + r_1 x_3 + r_2 x_3^2.$$

By applying shear free conditions at the top and bottom surface and shear continuity condition at the $x_{3(1)}$ interface, the first derivatives of out-of-plane displacement field can be eliminated from the in-plane displacement fields as follows,

$$u_{3,\alpha}^o = -\psi_{\alpha} - \frac{3h^2}{4} \phi_{\alpha} - \frac{h^2}{4} r_{2,\alpha} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} S_{\alpha}^{(k)}, \quad (2)$$

$$r_{1,\alpha} = -2\xi_{\alpha} - \frac{1}{h} \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} S_{\alpha}^{(k)},$$

$$r_{2,\alpha} = a_{\alpha\gamma}^{(1)} \phi_{\gamma} + b_{\alpha\gamma}^{(1)} S_{\gamma}^{(1)}.$$

So, the final displacement fields of C⁰-type efficient higher-order plate theory can be given by

$$u_{\alpha} = u_{\alpha}^o + \psi_{\alpha} x_3 + \xi_{\alpha} x_3^2 + \phi_{\alpha} x_3^3 + S_{\alpha}^{(1)} (x_3 - x_{3(1)}) H(x_3 - x_{3(1)}) + \sum_{k=2}^{N-1} (a_{\alpha\gamma}^{(1)} \phi_{\gamma}) (x_3 - x_{3(k)}) H(x_3 - x_{3(k)}) + \sum_{k=2}^{N-1} (b_{\alpha\gamma}^{(1)} S_{\gamma}^{(1)}) (x_3 - x_{3(k)}) H(x_3 - x_{3(k)}), \quad (3)$$

$$u_3 = u_3^o + r_1 x_3 + r_2 x_3^2.$$

The derivatives of out-of-plane displacement field have been taken out from the in-plane displacement fields, so that the C⁰ continuous element is only required for their finite element implementation. On the other hand, independent transverse stress fields, which are based on the seventh-order zig-zag model, can be expressed as follows,

$$\sigma_{3\alpha}^* = C_{3\alpha 3\beta} \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{\beta\gamma} \gamma_{3\alpha}^{(0)} + \mathcal{B}_{\beta\gamma} \gamma_{3\alpha}^{(1)} + \mathcal{C}_{\beta\gamma} \gamma_{3\alpha}^{(2)} \\ + \mathcal{D}_{\beta\gamma} \gamma_{3\alpha}^{(2)} + \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \gamma_{3\alpha}^{(2)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The relationship between displacement fields and independent transverse stress fields is achieved through the mixed variational theorem(MVT). In a full-length paper, numerical examples will be analyzed and the results obtained herein will be compared with those reported in literature to demonstrate the accuracy of the C⁰-type efficient higher-order plate theory. The derivation of the relationship and the equilibrium state will be described in detail.

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